

LOCAL CONTENT POLICY ON PETROLEUM SECTOR AND LOCAL TECHNOLOGY DEVELOPMENT IN NIGER DELTA REGION OF NIGERIA (2010-2023)

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ABSTRACT

This study was carried out to examine the influence of local content policy on petroleum sector on local technology in the Niger delta region of Nigeria from 2010-2023. The study was anchored on the dependency theory. Research design made use of questionnaire and interview was adopted for the study. Though, the population for the study was thirty million, five hundred and thirty four thousand, seven hundred and thirty five (30,534,785) of the six oil producing states in the Niger delta region, the determined sample size of five hundred and eighty seven (587) population gotten through Taro Yamene's formulae were used for the study. Both primary and secondary sources of data collection were adopted for the study. Stratified and purposive sampling techniques were used for the study. Data of the study were analysed used simple regression at 0.05 level of significance. Findings revealed that local content policy on petroleum sector has a significant influence on local technology development in the Niger delta of Nigeria. Having concluded that local content policy on petroleum sector can determine the rate of local technology development in the Niger delta region, it was recommended among others that Government should ensure that oil and gas sector operating in the Niger delta region are comply with the policy of making use of local technology for the enhancement of socio-economic development in the region.

KEYWORDS: Local content policy, local technology, socio-economic development, and Niger Delta region

INTRODUCTION

Prior to independence in 1960, the Nigeria government commenced effort to establish policies and measures to promote the development of local content in the oil and gas industry.

These measures were not considered comprehensive and also failed to achieve the desire objectives of indigenizing the industry and facilitating the diversification of Nigeria's economy. Nevertheless, Nigeria did not relent in its effort to initiate and establish a comprehensive policy for promoting the development of local content in the petroleum industry. The discovery of crude oil in the commercial quantity in the Bayelsa state in the Niger delta region before the independence was a blessing to Nigeria given the key role played by the petroleum industry in the country's economic development. The petroleum sector generates about 95 percent of total revenue and 80 per cent of natural income for Nigeria. To service the operations in the oil industry, Nigeria makes huge investments; spending over 86 billion annually (Gbegi & Adebisi 2013).

Despite this investment in the petroleum sector, it is presumable that some important macro variables have not fared well in terms of economic growth in the country in general; such as manpower/capacity development, transfer of technology; employment/local wealth creation; adequate care for the environment, inflation etc. Before the advent of local content policy (law), a significant proportion of government revenue in the oil and gas industry were paid to foreign contractors for services and procurement, resulting in capital flight and leaving very little for the country's industrial base and general economic development. It was noted that in the hydrocarbon industry, certain engineering services such as fabrication, engineering, procurement, construction, front-end and engineering design, are often carried out abroad where most of the equipment is manufactured thereby employing citizens of other countries at the detriments of Nigerians (Willie, Mboho and Udom, 2023).

The host communities in the Niger Delta region have had very little to show in terms of physical infrastructure and socio-economic development. The Niger Delta region cannot be compared to other regions of the world that are oil-producing in terms of infrastructural development, job creation, local wealth creation, and human capacity building, (Heum, *et.al* 2003; Willie, Mboho and Udom, 2023; Peters and Basseyy, 2019),

It is for this reason, that the Nigerian government enacted the local content (act) policy that was signed into law by the former president of the Federal Republic of Nigeria Goodluck Jonathan in April 2010. The policy sets a framework for higher participation of indigenous Nigerian operators in the oil and gas sector (petroleum industry) and added value to the nation's economy. The policy also include the stimulating of growth of Indigenous capacities, encourage small and medium scale businesses in the oil and gas industry, and local technology development to take active part in its operations for socio-economic development of the Niger Delta region. This research is to examine the influence of local content policy in petroleum sector on local technology development of the Niger Delta region from 2010-2023.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Local content policy on the petroleum sector was formulated for greater participation of indigenes in the petroleum industry in terms of policy formulation and implementation but may have failed to manifest in the oil-bearing communities in the Niger Delta region. Inordinate marginalization of the host communities of the petroleum industry by government and oil multinational companies has caused serious environmental degradation and poverty in the Niger Delta region (Udom, Mboho and Umo, 2024). This ugly situation has engendered insecurity, protest, agitation, and disruption of oil operations in the region. The issue of neglect and insincerity on the part of the government for genuine local wealth creation and

socio-economic development in the Niger Delta region has become a matter of great concern (Nigerian Liquefied Natural Gas Annual Report 2018). Recent statistical data from studies of the United Nations on the environment shows that there has been a wild spread of abject poverty and squalor among the people of the Niger Delta areas due to oil activities (UNDP 2019; Ateiret and Mboho, 2019).

Government's objectives for the local content policy initiative among others include promotion of indigenous participation and the fostering of skills and local technology transfer. (NOGICD Act, 2010; Mboho, 2021). The inability of the policy to address the major issues of the Niger Delta region as contained in the government's objectives for the benefit of the people as well as the socio-economic development of the Niger Delta region is worrisome. The main objective of this study is to examine the influence of Local Content Policy on the petroleum sector on local technology development in the Niger Delta Region in Nigeria. 2010-2023.

RESEARCH HYPOTHESES

Ho₁: Local Content Policy on the petroleum sector does not significantly influence local technology development in the Niger Delta Region in Nigeria.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Local Content Policy

Local content policies are policies imposed by the government that require firms to use domestically manufactured goods or domestically supplied services to operate in an economy (Fred & Evans, 2018). The purpose of Local Content Law is essentially to ensure the use of indigenous people (Nigerians) to execute certain assignments where they have the requisite skill and competence (The Nigerian Oil and Gas Industry Content Development Act, 2010). The policy is intended to build the capability of native firms and to provide more opportunities for partaking in trade and commerce. Therefore, it is expected that for most investments to be retained within local businesses, it is necessary to ensure the active involvement of local firms. The adoption of Local Content law is therefore seen as a strategy to add to the participation of indigenous firms to create more employment opportunities for the domestic labour force (Abdulkabir, Shaufique, Azmawani, and Siong, 2012).

Local Technology

It is widely accepted that for society at large to fully understand the issue and transform economically, industries need to embrace local technology in their operational approach. Technology means knowing how to do something. According to Merriam Webster learner's dictionary (2018), going local technologies could be described as technology employed by the native inhabitants of a country or nation and which constitute an important part of its cultural heritage and should therefore be protected against exploitation by industrialized countries. Warren et.al (2005) observed local technology as local knowledge that is unique to a given culture or society. Supporting the view, Grenier (1998) stressed that local technology is the unique, traditional, local knowledge existing within and developed around specific conditions of women and men indigenous to a particular geographic area. A particular commonality to be noted is that local technology generally refers to the matured long-standing traditions and practices of certain regional, indigenous, or local communities as well as the wisdom, knowledge, and teachings of these communities (Udoh and Mboho,

2026). Mboho (2019) characterized local technology in four things thus, as it is centred on local or indigenous peoples and their beliefs or practices; bound by geography in that the knowledge, most often, does not transcend the locality where it originates; tacit in nature, being most times orally passed from person to person, for generations; not dated in the sense that the knowledge or practices do not necessarily have to be primordial. Technologies employed by the native inhabitants of a country and which constitute an important part of its cultural heritage should be protected against exploitation by industrialized countries.

Borgmann, (2006) perceived Local technology as the systematic body of knowledge acquired by local people through the accumulation of experiences, informal experiments, and intimate understanding of the environment in a given culture. Nigeria especially the Niger Delta Region is greatly blessed with gifted hands that are laboriously engaged in various types of local technologies. There is hardly any part of the region that does not have remarkable local technology to show for its existence. The Indigenous industries among others include the production of pots from clay and aluminium metal scraps, textile making, cloth weaving, bronze casting, leather tanning, drilling, fabrication and assembling of tools and the like, in various parts of the country. The indigenous knowledge supporting these industries is generally passed on from generation to generation and hence it is a tradition in specific locations to produce specific products. The method of local technology transmission and skills acquisition is largely through observation and apprenticeship (National Centre for Technology Management, 2008).

Willie, *et.al* (2012) explain that when indigenous knowledge finds applications in tools, techniques, processes and methods that help in solving problems, local technologies arise. Local technology is the basis for local-level decision-making in industry, agriculture, healthcare, food preparation, education, natural resource management, and a host of other activities in rural communities. The Global Knowledge Conference (Toronto, June 1997) emphasized the urgent need to learn, preserve, and exchange local technology. In his recent call for a new inclusive approach to development, the President of the World Bank has stressed the need for a framework that deals *inter alia* with indigenous people and their technology.

Local Content Policy and Local Technology Development

Nigeria is dramatically evolving towards an emerging economy and she is desirous of becoming one of the World's twenty biggest economies in the twentieth century. Nigeria has encapsulated that desire into a strategic vision tagged 'Local Content Policy (Federal Republic of Nigeria 2000). The vision is also laden with the intent to promote indigenous participation in oil and gas sector, especially in local technology transfer, local workforce development and also on local workforce employment. It also aims to reduce the burden of poverty on the populace and to massively roll out infrastructure in large magnitudes through local technology transfer and development. For instance, the availability of infrastructure is the *sine qua non* for any sustainable development in the socio-economic planning of any society (Mboho, 2021). Nigeria's projection perhaps, is neither undue optimism nor an over-ambitious target when viewed upon the backdrop of the country being Africa's most populous country (a fifth of Sub-Saharan Africa) with an estimated population of over 140 million people and richly endowed with vast oil and gas resources. However, as promising as the policy seems, without commensurate investments in local technology and the adoption of

appropriate technologies to drive that policy, it might as well go the way of previous development plans initiated by the country since independence in 1960. The above argument is predicated upon the critical role local technology plays in socioeconomic development of nations, more so, for their competitiveness in a global context, a position reinforced by many development experts, scholars, and international development agencies (IDCs) (United Nations (UN) Millennium Project 2005). As people search for more and better ways to organize themselves to improve their socio-economic status, access to technology increasingly determines their success (The Smith Institute 2005), and with that same understanding that local technology and innovation have a vital role to play in boosting Africa's socio-economic development, especially in oil and gas sector, the eighth African Union (AU) Summit of heads of state and governments was convened in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia (Juma 2007).

As there is an observable global shift from an industrial to technological and then to knowledge- and information-based economies, driven by revolutionary developments in local technology (Imparato and Harari 1996 as cited in Khota and Pretorius 2008), In today's world, indigenous technologies (ICT) have a profound effect on most socio-economic, political and cultural aspects of society; they have become indispensable tools in the implementation of national development plans in many countries, supporting their efforts to secure the welfare and prosperity of their citizens (Mboho and Ibok, 2011). Thus, Section 41 (1) of the local content policy mandates for actualization of technology transfer. This involves the Minister making regulations setting out targets to ensure full utilization and steady growth of indigenous companies engaged in the exploration, seismic data processing, engineering design, reservoir studies, manufacturing and fabrication of equipment and other facilities and providing support services for the oil and gas industry in Nigeria.

There is no doubt that such a measure is geared towards not only complete take-over of management and administration of the sector by local Nigerians but to enable proficiency and competitiveness. The motive behind this provision is for Nigeria and Nigerians not to remain perpetual appendages to the foreign partners in the management and control of the oil and gas industry. This is to strengthen the succession plan for Indigenous Nigerians envisaged by the Act at the exit of the expatriates in order not to be a succession without success. This is an ambitious and laudable dream (Mboho, Udoh and Udo, 2019). Realization of technology transfer from the expatriate partners to Nigerians remains a cardinal objective of the Local Content Act. It is in this regard that *Section 44* of the Act provides that the operator shall submit to the Board annually a plan setting out a programme of planned initiatives aimed at promoting the effective transfer of technologies from the operator and alliance partners to Nigerian individuals and companies.

According to Farley (2005), it has become widely acknowledged that local technology play an instrumental role in the reduction of poverty, improvement of competitiveness, and delivering results in key sectors – education, agriculture, information and communication, transportation, biotechnology among others. He further maintained that the importance of local technology, including knowledge for development cannot be understated, as they are undeniably fundamental to the wealth and health of individuals. The UN Millennium Project (2005) asserts that the long-term driving force for modern economic growth has been science-based technological advances in its inclusion in local content policy. In corroboration of Farley (2005), the UN Millennium Project's (2005) statements, went a

step further to maintain that social development today is determined by the ability to establish a synergistic interaction between technological innovation and human values. This leads to a new set of organizations and institutions that create positive feedback loops between productivity, flexibility, solidarity, safety, participation and accountability, in a new model of development that could be socially and environmentally sustainable. Therefore, countries' science, technology, innovation and local content policies are designed to stimulate steady growth in gross domestic product (GDP), advance the quality of life for their citizens, improve skills and knowledge among the population, and so on.

However, Mboho and Inyang (2011) maintained that differences in growth due to the distribution, use, adoption, adaptation, and generation of knowledge are widening and that forces of globalization, rapidly changing technology, and the increasing importance of knowledge have raised the cost of having low capacity in science, technology, and knowledge for development capacity in developing countries. He, therefore, called for explicit efforts to increase technology flows. This scenario is also acute in Nigeria. In response to that call, a spectrum of pervasive local technology platforms through the initiation of local content must be identified as candidates for adoption if the country and other developing nations must improve the socio-economic status of their citizens through science, technology and innovation. Such platform (generic) technologies that have broad applications for or impacts on the economy include ICT, biotechnology, nanotechnology, and new materials (UN Millennium Project 2005).

Undeniably, local technology offers a new channel for economic growth which may allow developing countries to catch the development train faster and perhaps ensure a more sustainable ride. However, Baliamoune-Lutz (2003) once said, that technology per se does not solve social problems but rather its availability and use. Likewise, Technology on its own will not be able to solve social problems, but its availability and wide application in society is the prerequisite for economic and social development in our world (Castells, 1999). Once more, technologies are helping to integrate diverse economic fields in new ways and have consequently been seen as generic tools that underpin most other economic sectors (Juma 2007).

Nevertheless, technology transfer tends to focus on the producer of the technology while much of the focus of diffusion relates to the end user of the technology. As such, viewing the issue from a holistic perspective of technology development and utilization, these two areas are closely interrelated and must be considered together (Ahmed 2005). Chinn and Fairlie (2006) argue that rates of technology use differ markedly across countries hence it is necessary to adopt local technology within its territorial boundaries.

Oyekanmi (2005) stated that the relevance of indigenous technology to the development of individuals, organizations, nations and the entire world cannot be over-emphasized, for the world today is shaped by advancements in the field of ICT. Indeed, the contributions of indigenous technology to socio-economic development have been highlighted by very many researchers and development experts alike. Details of the role played by indigenous technology in a global context can be found elsewhere in the UN Millennium Project (2005). For instance, the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) has this to say: Indigenous technology is perhaps the central development issue at the dawn of the new millennium. Not only are the technologies the key to economic growth, they can also impact on most pressing global issues (UNDP 2001).

Peter and Waribugo (2022), investigated Local Content Strategy Implementation in Nigeria: Challenges and Prospects. The purpose of this study is to identify the challenges that have affected the effective implementation of the local content policy as a strategy on the operations of the Nigeria oil and gas industry and to explore the prospects synergistic work system offers to ameliorate the identified challenges. The study took a qualitative approach in which a conceptual framework was developed from reviewing existing literature on the subject matter of local content policy and synergism as an operations strategy. The findings show that synergy amongst the local or Indigenous oil and gas companies in the form of sequential integration and synergetic alignment is one veritable strategy to combat the challenges of capital formation, technology acquaintance and effective delivery process thus enabling the full realisation of the main objectives of the local content policy. The practical implication is that indigenous oil and gas companies can venture into the capital-intensive aspects of the industry through synergy. The limitation of this study is that it is heavily reliant on a literature review and therefore lends itself open to a future quantitative study to determine the level of significance the two dimensions of synergistic work systems (Sequential Integration and Synergetic Alignment) will have on cost minimisation and quality assurance of local content operators in Nigeria's oil and gas industry. However, the originality and value of this study stems from the fact that the importance of synergistic work system on the local content policy strategy has not been fully explored in literature especially with regards to flexibility and delivery which are vital elements of operations strategy.

Babatunde (2021), analyses Local Participation Policy on Her Investment Climate. This research study employs an analytical approach, more specifically qualitative analysis, in analyzing the interplay between the various factors which have birthed low oil and gas productivity in the Niger Delta region of Nigeria and how proper application of Nigeria's local participation policy can influence the circumstances and yield positive results. The research study will rely heavily on available literature and legislative enactments, as well as available case law on the issues concerned. The primary sources in the collection of materials for this paper comprise of journals, books, and articles which address the relevant research questions guiding the scope of this paper. The study reveals that long-term benefits of local content policy such as technology transfer, long-term fiscal incentives, and the growth of local commerce and industry, will go a long way in setting Nigeria on a plain path to sustainable economic growth and better resource management. The Nigerian government must play its role in driving local content policy by facilitating Nigerian enterprises to take an active part in the local content programs, as well as keep tabs and monitor the effectiveness of local content policy in achieving its targets (Mboho and Ibok, 2021).

James (2014), studied Local Content Policy, Human Capital Development and Sustainable Business Performance in the Nigerian Oil and Gas Industry. This study examined the extent to which the Local Content Policy has impacted human capital development and sustainable business performance in the Nigerian Oil and Gas Industry, following the enactment of enabling legislation. Primary data were employed, which were obtained through the administration of a structured questionnaire to purposively selected oil servicing companies in the Niger Delta, the home to more than eighty per cent of the Indigenous oil companies in Nigeria. The results showed that Local Content Policy had significant impact on the development of human capital in the Oil and Gas Industry. There was a paradigm shift in

the educational capacity of the Management of the oil servicing firms as over 70% of them had at least a first degree or its equivalent. Through oil sector linkages, the firms strengthened their absorptive capacities to internalize the technological and managerial skills that flow to them. This consequently boosted the business performance of indigenous oil servicing firms in terms of growth in profit, market share and return on investment (ROI). The study concluded that the Local Content Policy had achieved significant success in enhancing the development of human capital which in turn positively influenced business performance of indigenous companies in the Oil and Gas Industry in Nigeria (Mboho and Inynag, 2011).

Ayonmike and Okeke (2015) investigated the Nigerian Local Content Act and its Implication on Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) and The Nation's Economy. Using secondary data, the paper examined the Nigerian Local Content Act, Technical and Vocational Education Training (TVET) and the implication of the Local Content Act on TVET and the Nigerian economy. The paper observed that in Nigeria, Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) has received a lot of value from Nigerian local Content Act. The position of the paper is that for Nigeria to achieve the intended goals and objectives of the Local Content Act, the government, stakeholders, and the board in charge of implementation and monitoring of the Local Content Act must first of all revitalize Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) institutions. There should also be instituted training and retraining of Technical and Vocational Education professionals, that will help produce the skilled work force needed to implement the Nigerian Local Content Act.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Dependency Theory of International Relations

Dependency theory was developed from a 0- perspective by Paul Baran in 1957 with the publication of his *The Political Economy of Growth* (Vernengo, 2004). The theory was popular in the 1960s and 1970s as a criticism of modernization theory, which was falling increasingly out of favour because of continued widespread poverty in much of the world. At that time the assumptions of liberal theories of development were under attack (Caves, 2004). It was used to explain the causes of over-urbanization, a theory that urbanization rates outpaced industrial growth in several developing countries (Shandra, John; London, Bruce; Williamson, and John 2003). Dependency theory is the idea that resources flow from a “periphery” of poor and underdeveloped states to a “core” of wealthy states, enriching the latter at the expense of the former. A central contention of dependency theory is that poor states are impoverished and rich ones enriched by the way poor states are integrated into the “world system”. This theory was officially developed in the late 1960s following World War II, as scholars searched for the root issue of the lack of development in Latin America (Ahiakpor, 1985).

The theory arose as a reaction to modernization theory, an earlier theory of development which held that all societies progress through similar stages of development, that today's underdeveloped areas are thus in a similar situation to that of today's developed areas at some time in the past, and that, therefore, the task of helping the underdeveloped areas out of poverty is to accelerate them along this supposed common path of development, by various means such as investment, technology transfer, and closer integration into the world market. Dependency theory rejected this view, arguing that underdeveloped countries are not

merely primitive versions of developed countries, but have unique features and structures of their own; and, importantly, they are in the situation of being the weaker members in a world market economy (Newschool, 2009).

Some writers have argued for its continuing relevance as a conceptual orientation to the global division of wealth (James, 1997). Dependency theorists can typically be divided into two categories: liberal reformists and neo-Marxists. Liberal reformists typically advocate for targeted policy interventions; while the neo-Marxists believe in a command-centred economy. According to Osvaldo (1969) dependency is used to explain the economic development of a state in terms of the external influences which may be political, economic, and cultural on national development policies. Dependency theory is a historical condition which shapes a certain set of structures of the world economy such that it favours some countries to the detriment of others, especially the third-world countries, and limits the development possibilities of the subsidiary economies to a condition in which the economy of a certain group of countries is restrained by the development and expansion of another financial system, to which their own is subjected (Theotonio, 1971). Indeed, their studies suggested that “economic activity in the richer countries (developed world) often led to serious economic problems in the poorer countries”. The solution to this in the words of Vincent (2008) is that poorer countries should embark on programs of import substitution so that they need not purchase the manufactured products from the richer countries. Even though the poorer countries would still sell their primary products on the world market, their foreign exchange reserves would not be used to purchase manufactured products from abroad. These countries are not "behind" or "catching up" to the richer countries of the world. They are not poor because they lagged behind the scientific transformations or the enlightenment values of the European states. They are poor because they were forcefully incorporated into the European economic system only as producers of raw materials or to serve as repositories of low-priced labour, and were denied the opportunity to sell their God-given possessions in any way that competed with leading states Vincent (2008).

The theory therefore opines that substitute use of resources is preferable to the resource usage patterns imposed by developed and dominant economies. Proponents of dependency theory rely upon a belief that there exist clear “state” economic interests which ought to be articulated for each country. Dependent states, therefore, should opt for policies of self-reliance. In other words, greater integration into the global financial system is not necessarily a good choice for poor countries; rather a policy of self-reliance should be viewed as opting for a strategy of restricted exchanges with the world financial system. Poor countries should only support exchanges on terms that promise to improve the social and financial welfare of the larger citizenry in the state.

Relevant of the Theory

Dependency theory is adopted for this study because the theory advocates a voluntary relationship with other countries. Local Content Act adopted by the Nigerian government is a voluntary measure to be self-reliant and get economic freedom and advancement from the grips of European advanced industrial economies and their dominant multinational corporations having their firms in different parts of the country. The theory therefore opines that substitute use of resources is preferable to the resource usage patterns imposed by developed and dominant economies. Proponents of dependency theory rely upon a belief that

there exist clear “state” economic interests which ought to be articulated for each country.

METHODOLOGY

This research adopted a descriptive and cross-sectional survey design. The study area was the Niger Delta region. Although the entire Niger Delta region is made up of nine states (Rivers, Delta, Akwa Ibom, Imo, Ondo, Edo, Cross River, Abia and Bayelsa) the study population in this research was only six oil-producing states (Akwa Ibom, Bayelsa, Delta, Rivers, Cross River, and Abia States) within the Niger Delta region. Thus, the population of the study was 30,534,785. The sample size was 589; this was determined using the Taro Yamani formula. However, the main instrument used in collecting data for this study was a well-designed questionnaire. The data were analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. The descriptive statistics was frequency count and percentage analysis while the inferential statistics used the regressions analysis. The regression analysis was adopted to test the stated hypotheses at a 0.01 level of significance. This was to establish the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable.

RESULT

Test of hypothesis and Discussion of findings

Test of Hypothesis

H₀: Local Content policy on the petroleum sector does not significantly influence local technology development in the Niger Delta Region of Nigeria.

H₁: Local Content policy on the petroleum sector has significantly influenced local technology development in the Niger Delta Region of Nigeria.

Regression Analysis Result on the influence of Local Content policy on the petroleum sector on local technology development in the Niger Delta Region of Nigeria.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.601 ^a	.361	.325	9.10436

Goodness of Fit ^a

Mmodel	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	106.136	1	4592.136	8.823	.001 ^b
Residual	132.028	230	213.258		
Total	238.164	231			

Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
		B	Std. Error	Beta	T	Sig.
1	(Constant)	1.515	.131		1.226	.003
	local content policy	.526	.243	.483	2.165	.000

A. Predictors: (Constant), **local Content policy on Petroleum Sector**

B. Dependent Variable: **local Technology Development**

Source: Researcher's Computation

Table 1: shows the result of regression analysis on the influence of Local Content policy on the petroleum sector and local technology development in the Niger Delta Region of Nigeria. The generalized model summary showed a R^2 of 0.361 implies that 36.1% of the Local Content policy on the petroleum sector influences 36.1% of the local technology development in the Niger Delta Region of Nigeria. The model also showed a goodness of fit at 95 per cent (p -value <0.05). The relationship between Local Content policy on the petroleum sector and local technology development in the Niger Delta Region of Nigeria was statistically significant at 95% (also p -value <0.05). In line with this result, the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant relationship between Local Content policy on the petroleum sector and local technology development in the Niger Delta Region of Nigeria was thus rejected. Hence, it was concluded that Local Content policy on the petroleum sector has a significant influence on local technology development in the Niger Delta Region of Nigeria

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

This study was to examine the influence of Local Content policy on the petroleum sector on local technology development in the Niger Delta Region of Nigeria.; the hypothesis on this objective was, there is no significant relationship between Local Content policy in the petroleum sector and local technology development in the Niger Delta Region of Nigeria. In the test of hypothesis, it was revealed that Local Content policy on the petroleum sector significantly influenced local technology development in the Niger Delta Region of Nigeria.

Realization of technology transfer from the expatriate partners to Nigerians remains a cardinal objective of the Local Content Act. It is in this regard that *Section 44* of the Act provides that the operator shall submit to the Board annually a plan setting out a programme of planned initiatives aimed at promoting the effective transfer of technologies from the operator and alliance partners to Nigerian individuals and companies. The result support the finding Tokyo (2008) who stated that local policy implementation encourage local technology which increase efficiency, provide access to new markets or services, create new opportunities for income generation and improving governance and give poor people a voice. In another light, Ndukwe (2008) noted that, the emergence of homemade technologies has led to improvements in efficiency and productivity, a reduction in transaction costs, increased service innovation and a better quality of life.

Thus, Section 41 (1) of the local content policy mandates for actualization of technology transfer. This involves the Minister making regulations setting out targets to ensure full utilization and steady growth of indigenous companies engaged in the exploration, seismic data processing, engineering design, reservoir studies, manufacturing and fabrication of equipment and other facilities and provides support services for the oil and gas industry in Nigeria. However, from our research, it was revealed that most of the oil and gas firms make use of local technologies and tools in their operations. Some of the frequently used ones are; shale shakers, degasser, mud cleaners, sand pumps, and stabbing guides as shown below;

Made in Nigeria sand pump use for oil drilling

Made in Nigeria Sg5-1/2 Stabbing Guide for Oil Drill Pipe

Made in Nigeria Drilling Mud Shale Shaker for Linear Motion Solid Control

CONCLUSION

The study established that adequate implementation of Local content policy of petroleum sector influences local technology development in the Niger Delta Region. The result of test of hypothesis indicated that Local Content policy on petroleum sector has a significant influence on local technology development in the Niger Delta Region of Nigeria. In line with this result, it was concluded that Content policy on petroleum sector can determine the rate of local technology development in the Niger Delta Region of Nigeria.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- i. Government should ensure that Multinational companies are liaise with the relevant agencies to organize, fund and equip training programme related to local technology for the indigenes of Niger Delta Region. This is to ensure that local technology or tools are always available, useful and also meet the required standard in the petroleum sector.
- ii. Government should also assist local firm financially to upgrade their technology in order to properly service oil and gas sector.
- iii. Government should ensure that the oil and gas sector operating in the Niger Delta region complies with the policy of making use of local technology for the enhancement of socio-economic development in the region.

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